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Research Ethics: The Backbone of Scientific Integrity

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ABSTRACT

The aim of research is to create and expand knowledge which has a great positive impact on societal values, promoting technology, influencing various disciplines, and shaping scientific development. In view of the importance of research, it is expedient that a robust foundational framework is instituted to ensure the enthronement of integrity, accountability, transparency and respect for subjects including the environment during research. It is important that research ethics is not mistaken as the same thing as research morals. While research ethics are defined external principles and set rules that guide responsible conduct in research; research morals are just internal values and beliefs that shape researcher's personal judgment in interpreting ethical guidelines. This best practice starts with the definition of boundaries within the context of research, stating the professional ethics that govern such research. Major principles of research including confidentiality, objectivity, informed consent, and the use of data must be outlined and adhered to if the results of the research must be respected and upheld. Ethics is indispensably necessary in every profession as it forms the basis through which institutions, employees, disciplines admit new members, while holding old members accountable.

Keywords: Ethical standard, ethical dilemmas, misconduct, research morals, ethical guidelines, confidentiality, objectivity, fabrication, falsification, plagiarism, informed consent.

INTRODUCTION

The pursuit of knowledge has exposed many researchers to a lot of information that must be treated with the utmost professionalism and integrity. Professional ethics in research are those standards and principles that guide these researchers in ensuring they conduct their work with the required accountability and respect. Ethical responsibility extends far beyond merely following rules; they demand every researcher to conduct themselves properly by imbibing honesty, transparency, and respect for subjects. Ethical research also does more than protection of participants' rights (Murphy and Dingwall 2001).

Upholding ethical standards in research is a professional necessity that ensures the integrity, credibility, and reliability of scientific investigations. Research ethics plays a vital role in promoting responsible research practices, protecting human subjects, and maintaining public trust in the scientific community. The importance of research ethics cannot be overstated, as it provides a framework for researchers to conduct their work with honesty, transparency, and accountability (WHO, 2017). Similarly, the need for ethical standard in research is crucial to ensure the integrity, credibility, and reliability of scientific investigations. Research ethics promotes responsible research practice and protecting human subject (Resink, D. B, 2019).

Research misconduct, including fabrication, falsification, and plagiarism, can have severe consequences, damaging not only the researcher's reputation but also the credibility of the scientific community. Institutional policies and regulatory guidelines are essential in preventing research misconduct and promoting ethical research practices. Organizations such as the World Health Organization (WHO) and the European Commission have established codes of conduct and guidelines for research integrity, emphasizing the need for transparency, accountability, and responsible innovation (WHO, 2017 & European Commission, 2020).

It is critical to uphold professional ethics especially in this era of increasing rate of data intrusion, plagiarism, falsification, fabrication and lots more. These misconducts, in addition to undermining the authenticity of research outcomes, erode public trust in every aspect of science and academia. Deliberate enforcement of total adherence to professional ethics should be strengthened to achieve the aim of research in contributing to three-sixty-degrees societal advancement.

This paper thus explores the major components of professional ethics in research, it examines the litany of ethical challenges and emphasizes the need for professional ethics in providing and maintaining an environment of trust and equity. The difficulties of carrying out research in accordance with ethical norms were also discussed and addressed because there is a need for constant introspection and review. The paper outlined the practical demonstration of the ways in which research ethics can help in advancing the

aims and objectives of research and in promoting public trust in research results which form part of the primary goal of this paper.

Statement of the Problem

In this era of technology, research environment should at least boast of the integrity of scientific inquiry in the promotion of knowledge, policy advancement, and societal conviction. Despite the litany of ethical codes, regulatory guidelines, and institutional outlines meant to discourage irresponsible conduct, violation of professional ethics in research has not ceased to exist. Reports of plagiarism, falsification, inappropriate authorship, and hosts of others continued to rear her ugly face in the professional and academic environment.

These behaviors compromise the integrity and reliability of research works, thereby eroding societal trust in science, cause irreparable damage to institutional reputations which may lead to academic regression. Career pressure, publication demands, or environment may be the reasons those that engage in this practice have, however, there is no reason good enough to encourage misconduct.

The problems addressed in this paper are the unending cases of research ethics violations which compromise the integrity of scientific knowledge and undermine the reliability of research. Few of the challenges which this paper examined included inconsistent but poor enforcement of policies, poor awareness, poor level of education on ethical norms, institutional hurdles that have permitted this misconduct to go unhindered. The examination of these barriers exposed the immediate and root causes of ethical lapses in research and has suggested strategies to advance a culture of accountability, transparency, and integrity among researchers especially in academic and institutional environments.

Aims and Objectives

The main aim of this paper is to examine ethical standards in research. Specifically, the study sought to:

1. To examine the principles of research ethics, their importance and benefits in the research practices.
2. To investigate the ethical guidelines and codes in research.
3. Identify the types of research misconducts.
4. Examine the influence of professional ethical codes in research.
5. Assess the challenges of research ethics.
6. To suggest the methods for addressing ethical challenges in research.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

1. What are the principles of research ethics, their importance and benefits in the research practices?
2. What are the ethical guidelines and codes in research?
3. What are the types of research misconducts, like plagiarism, falsification, and fabrications?
4. How do professional ethical codes influence research integrity?
5. What are the challenges of research ethics?
6. How can professional ethics in research be strengthened?

Scope of the work

The scope of this paper is to define research ethics and their importance in academic and professional disciplines. Carry out an in-dept analysis of research misconduct. Examine the roles of ethical standards, institutional guidelines, and regulatory framework in ensuring research validity. Also enumerate the challenges facing acceptable ethical behavior and identify best strategies in promoting transparency and integrity of research.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Conceptual Framework

What is Research Ethics?

Research ethics has to do with the set of principles and guidelines that govern the way research is carried out. Research ethics has to do with the conduct of research in a way that protects and serves the interests of all subjects - individuals, groups and/or society (Temidayo O, n.d).

Research ethics ensures that the quest for more knowledge must respect the rights, dignity and welfare of the subjects while aiming for positive contribution of research to the society.

Principles of Research Ethics

These are foundational frameworks designed to help researchers in their research works. Integrity, accountability, respect for humans, and beneficence are some of the great pillars anchoring the ethics of research. Although, according to the Belmont Report by the National Commission for the Protection of Human Subjects of Biomedical and Behavioral Research, Respect for humans, beneficence, and justice are the three pillars around which the ethics of research are built (Kapil Dev: 2024). Both positions above are correct as human dignity is acknowledged and would be prioritized by ensuring that research subjects are adequately respected in making their own informed consent choices in the research studies.

Key Principles

1. **Respect for Persons:** Researchers must respect the autonomy and dignity of participants, ensuring that they are fully informed and able to make decisions about their involvement in the research (National Commission for the Protection of Human Subjects of Biomedical and Behavioral Research, 1979).
2. **Beneficence:** Researchers should maximize benefits and minimize harm to participants, ensuring that the research is conducted in a way that promotes the well-being of individuals and society (Beauchamp, T. L., & Childress, J. F. , 2013)).
3. **Non-Maleficence:** Researchers should do no harm to participants, avoiding actions that could cause physical, emotional, or psychological harm (World Medical Association, 2013).
4. **Autonomy:** Researchers should respect participants' autonomy, ensuring that they are free to make decisions about their involvement in the research without coercion or undue influence (National Commission for the Protection of Human Subjects of Biomedical and Behavioral Research, 1979).
5. **Justice:** Researchers should promote fairness and equity in the research, ensuring that benefits and burdens are distributed fairly and that participants are not exploited or marginalized (Emanuel, E. J., et al., 2004).
6. **Honesty and Transparency:** Researchers should conduct their work with integrity, avoiding falsification, fabrication, and plagiarism, and being transparent about their methods and findings (Resnik, D. B. , 2019).
7. **Confidentiality and Privacy:** Researchers should protect participants' personal information and maintain confidentiality, ensuring that data is collected and stored securely (National Research Council. , 2014).

The principles of research ethics are essential for promoting responsible research practices, protecting human subjects, and maintaining public trust in the scientific community. By adhering to these principles, researchers can ensure that their work is conducted with integrity, promoting the well-being of individuals and society.

Importance of Principles of Research Ethics

The principles of research ethics are essential for promoting responsible research practices, protecting human subjects, and maintaining public trust in the scientific community. These principles ensure that research is conducted with integrity, promoting the well-being of individuals and society.

Key Importance

1. **Protecting Human Subjects:** Research ethics principles protect participants from harm, exploitation, and abuse, ensuring their safety and well-being (National Commission for the Protection of Human Subjects of Biomedical and Behavioral Research. , 1979).
2. **Promoting Research Integrity:** Research ethics principles promote honesty, transparency, and accountability in research, ensuring that findings are reliable and valid (Resnik, D. B. , 2019).
3. **Maintaining Public Trust:** Research ethics principles help build trust between researchers and the public, ensuring that research is conducted in a responsible and respectful manner (Shamoo, A. E., & Resnik, D. B. , 2015).

4. **Ensuring Validity and Reliability:** Research ethics principles ensure that research is conducted in a way that promotes validity and reliability, reducing the risk of errors and biases (National Research Council. , 2014).
5. **Fostering Responsible Innovation:** Research ethics principles promote responsible innovation, ensuring that research is conducted in a way that considers the potential consequences and benefits for society (European Commission. , 2020).

Benefits

1. **Improved Research Quality:** Research ethics principles promote high-quality research that is reliable, valid, and generalizable (National Research Council. , 2014).
2. **Increased Public Trust:** Research ethics principles help build trust between researchers and the public, promoting confidence in research findings (Shamoo, A. E., & Resnik, D. B. , 2015).
3. **Protection of Vulnerable Populations:** Research ethics principles protect vulnerable populations, such as children, elderly, and those with disabilities, from exploitation and harm (National Commission for the Protection of Human Subjects of Biomedical and Behavioral Research. , 1979).
4. **Promotion of Responsible Research Practices:** Research ethics principles promote responsible research practices, reducing the risk of research misconduct and promoting a culture of integrity (Resnik, D. B. , 2019).

Ethical Guidelines and Codes

Ethical guidelines and codes provide the frameworks researchers and other stakeholders use in guarantying that research is carried out with utmost respect, integrity, and transparency to protect participants, demand accountability from researchers, and promote integrity of science.

Some critical codes and guidelines are:

- **Nuremberg Code (1947)** – this was developed after the Nuremberg trial of Nazi doctors after the WWII. It was resolved that voluntary informed consent is important; research ought to benefit society; unnecessary physical and mental pain should be avoided; freedom of participants to opt out without penalty.
- **Declaration of Helsinki (1964)** - The World Medical Association (WMA) during the 18th WMA General Assembly, Helsinki, Finland, June 1964 developed the Declaration of Helsinki as a statement of ethical principles for medical research involving human subjects, including research on identifiable human material and data (The World Medical Association). This code emphasized ethical review by independent committee; fundamentality of informed consent; participants' welfare.
- **Belmont Report (1979)** - The Belmont Report summarized the basic ethical principles identified by the Commission as three basic principles, among those generally accepted as cultural tradition are particularly relevant to the ethics of research involving human subjects: the principles of respect of persons, beneficence and justice (The Belmont Report 1979)).
- **UNESCO Universal Declaration on Bioethics and Human Rights (2005)** – this declaration focused on integration of ethics into all life sciences and respect for human dignity. Major key points it emphasized included cultural diversity and pluralism, social responsibility and health, equity, justice and equality, personal integrity and respect for human vulnerability.
- **Council for International Organization of Medical Sciences (CIOMS)** – This is an international, non-governmental, non-profit organization established jointly by WHO and UNESCO in 1949. The focus is ethical standards for biomedical research in international and low-resource settings. Emphasis is on cultural sensitivity, community engagement, fair participant selection, post-research gains for participants.
- **International Council for Harmonization (ICH) – Good Clinical Practice** – the focus is clinical trials involving human subjects. This group's priorities are credible and scientifically valid data; rights, safety, and well-being of trial subjects; clear definition of responsibilities for sponsors, investigators, and monitors.

Data Management Ethics

The Data management ethics has to do with assurance on data collection, storage, usage, and sharing. This must be done responsibly and ethically, with emphasis on fairness, transparency, accountability, and privacy. The use of data so that harm is minimized and positive outcomes for individuals and society is championed (Caterine Cote (2021)).

The principles of the data management ethics are though not limited to the following:

- **Ownership**

The ownership of individual information belongs to that individual. People's personal information must be taken with full authorization from the person. It is a crime and unethical to use people's information without their consent. There are many ways to seek approval to use one's personal or company's information. Agreement must be reached prior to use of the person's or company's information, otherwise it may lead to legal action.

- **Transparency**

Transparency is important when gathering, storing or using data. People must be free to know how their data is collected, used or stored. Researchers must be willing to make this information known to the subjects to allow them to decide whether to accept the agreement or not.

Denying the subjects the knowledge or deceiving them is both unethical and illegal. The affected subjects may seek redress from a court of law.

- **Privacy**

Researchers or scientists must be responsible enough to treat people's data with utmost respect. People's data must be stored in a secure database devoid of public interference. Several robust methods used for securing people's data must be deployed. To reduce errors in handling and analyzing sensitive data, de-identify the dataset. This will enable researchers or analysts to use data without necessarily attaching specific data points to individual identities.

- **Intention**

It's not ethical to collect their people's data for the sole purpose of harming them or putting them in the line of fire. Ensure that you have good intentions before collecting data.

Researchers should be careful with sensitive information. Unnecessary data should not be collected, especially sensitive ones. Try to minimize usage of data when it is not important, this will enable you to avoid unethical behavior.

- **Outcomes**

The outcome of data analysis is important whether with good or bad intentions. There is possibility of having disparate impact that is causing harm to people even with good intentions.

According to Harvard Professor, Latanya Sweeney, an example of disparate impact was when she searched for her name online, and an advertisement came up that read, "Latanya Sweeney, Arrested?" She had never been arrested. It was shocking to her.

One way of avoiding this disparate impact is to be intentional when analyzing data, although you may not have knowledge of the impact until the analysis is completed.

Research Misconduct

Research misconduct is actions or behaviours exhibited by researchers that undermine the integrity of the research. Research misconduct is committed when there is deliberate deviation from established ethical research practices.

The office of Research Integrity defines research misconduct as the falsification, fabrication or plagiarism in conducting, planning, reporting or reviewing research (Elizabeth George, 2023). The Office of Science and Technology Policy (OSTP) in the executive office of the President of US as part of its Federal Policy on Research Misconduct adopted in year 2000, Falsification, Fabrication, and Plagiarism (FFP) as major research misconducts. These three key research misconducts are defined under types of research misconduct below.

There are different types of research misconduct. However, three of them, namely plagiarism, falsification and fabrication have been marked as ‘cardinal sins’ of research misconduct.

Types of Research Misconduct

Different schools of thought have their different opinions on the types of research misconduct. One of the schools of thought stated that research misconduct include: falsification, fabrication, plagiarism, authorship issues, undeclared conflict of interest, suspected manipulation of peer review, manipulation of citation, and violation of research ethics. Another school of thought opined that the following are types of research misconduct, fabrication, falsification, plagiarism, inappropriate authorship, conflict of interest. In all this, there are three types of research misconduct that are regarded more serious than others. The first three listed misconducts, plagiarism, fabrication and falsification are the heinous misconducts.

Let us briefly explain the enumerated research misconduct:

Plagiarism

The simple definition of plagiarism is the act of using people’s idea or work without acknowledging them. It is one of the common acts of research misconduct. European Code of Conduct for research integrity defined plagiarism as the act of using other people’s works or ideas without giving proper credit to the original source, thereby violating the rights of the original author(s) to their intellectual outputs (The European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity revised edition, 2017).

Plagiarism threatens the integrity of research outcomes and can have both ethical and legal consequences. Plagiarism is a plague that must be tackled with every seriousness, it occurs at any stage, from conceptualization of the idea to publication of the work (Flinta, et al, 2023).

Plagiarism occurs in many forms which include blatant plagiarism, technical plagiarism, patchwork plagiarism, and self-plagiarism. Be it as it may, plagiarism diminishes research integrity and must be seen as unacceptable in research. Researchers must adhere to the tips on how to avoid this monster that eats the fabrics of research integrity (Deepak Juyal, et al, 2015).

The ability to detect plagiarism and effectively prosecute and punish the offenders must be strengthened.

Fabrication

Fabrication is regarded as one of the three ‘cardinal sins’ of research misconduct. The other two are plagiarism and falsification (Google June 09, 2025). Fabrication is the deliberate creation and/or inclusion of observation, data, or characterization which were absent when data was collected, or experiment was ran. Fabrication is also When claims are based on incomplete or assumed data analysis result.

Falsification

Falsification, a member of the three cardinal sins of research misconduct is when research results are altered or overlooked to support claims or hypotheses. When data is distorted through manipulation of any representation, process, equipment or image, falsification is committed.

Inappropriate Authorship

Care must be taken to avoid inappropriate authorship. Assigning authors without contribution to research, omitting original authors of research, naming authors incorrectly or in the wrong order, or naming authors without their informed consent is unethical and regarded as research misconduct.

Conflict of Interest Concealment

To avoid any ethical issues, conflict of interest which may be personal, financial, or professional must be declared in the research work. Conflict of interest is one of the misconducts that are classified under general misconduct. It is not as grievous as the cardinal sins of research misconducts.

Excuses for Research Misconduct

There are many reasons or excuses put forward for research misconduct which include but not limited to the following (Elizabeth George , 2023):

- **Personal Psychology**
The desire to attain a certain professional class or make financial gain may cause some researchers to commit research misconduct.
- **Career Pressure**

Career pressure is one of the main reasons researchers fall into the dungeon of research misconduct. The pressure to carry out research and publish within a period coupled with other personal responsibilities can push some to research misconduct. Although, no reason is adequate to justify a misconduct.

- **Carelessness**
Another reason for research misconduct is carelessness of researchers. Some of them take for granted the correct assigning of authors or omit original authors in their research works. A researcher must be intentional in his works to ensure he/she carried out the research meticulously.
- **Insufficient supervision**
Researchers must be trained adequately or have required skills to conduct research. The young ones must have supervisors or mentors that will guide them to avoid ethical issues. Absence of oversight or mentoring can inadvertently or advertently cause research misconduct.
- **Inadequate Knowledge**
Limited knowledge on research topics may lead researchers to research misconduct. Careless research conduct and reporting are regarded as misconduct.

There is no reason enough to justify research misconduct; any misconduct must be punished appropriately for deterrence.

Professional Ethical Codes in Research

Research ethics is a corner stone of scientific inquiry, ensuring that investigations are conducted with integrity, respect, and responsibility. Professional ethical codes in research provide a framework for researcher to navigate complex ethical dilemmas, promoting trust, credibility, and validity in research findings. These codes are essential for protecting human subjects, promoting research integrity, and fostering a culture of responsibility in the scientific. The most ethical codes cover the following areas (Md. Yeasir Arafat, 2024):

1. **Honesty & Integrity:** It is important to act with sincerity always. As a researcher, you must report your research including your methods. The data used, the results, whether published earlier, must be accurately reported with integrity. Researchers must not in any way mislead or try to mislead anyone, especially when working within a team. Keep to any agreements always.
2. **Respect for Intellectual Property:** Plagiarism is copying and claiming other people's work without giving credit to or referencing them. It is an offence and must be avoided by any means possible. We must respect copyrights and patents by seeking permission before using people's data, methods, findings etc. You should never plagiarize or copy other people's work or try to pass it off as your own. It is better to avoid the risk of plagiarism by acknowledging or referencing sources of data or information in your research.
3. **Transparency:** Be prepared to share your available data and results, including any new developed devices. Be mindful that publishing your findings will attract both praise and criticism. While findings deemed good will help in knowledge increase and advancement, we should be open to criticism and opinions of others for a healthy discussion and growth.
4. **Responsible and Legal Publication:** Researchers must be abreast of laws and regulations governing their choice of career or work and comply with them. Researchers should always publish new works and not copy or claim other's work.
5. **Confidentiality:** Another ethical principle of research is confidentiality. It is important that any information sourced during research work is treated with respect, including data from anonymous respondents. Researchers must comply with guidelines on the protection of classified information in line with relevant standards. This does not mean exposing research participants and putting them in the line of fire. People at risk must be protected.
6. **Carefulness:** Carelessness must be avoided while carrying out research to avoid mistakes that might put the researcher and his work at risk. Researchers must be meticulous, ensure their work is

reviewed properly for credibility. Documentation is also another important aspect of carefulness because it helps the researcher to make quick references.

7. **Objectivity:** Researchers must be objective in rolling out findings and suggestions. Every aspect of the research should be free from bias, whether in design, data analysis, interpretation, or peer review. Conflict of interest must be disclosed, avoid it if it affects the research negatively.
8. **Animal Care:** Researchers should care for and respect animals that are used for research purposes. Ensure that your experiments are both necessary and well-designed prior to the use of these animals.
9. **Human Subjects Protection:** Humans that participate in research must be taken care of by ensuring they are not exposed to harmful environment. The timeline planned for the research must be adhered to, thereby avoiding unnecessary exposure to stress, especially children, older ones and those with special needs. The right to privacy of the participants must be respected.

Challenges of Research Ethics

Researchers face enormous challenges on ethics while carrying out their work due to lack of globally accepted standard method of research work, competing interest, absence of defined guidelines, etc. (Kapil Dev, 2024)

1. **Ethical Dilemmas:** Ethical dilemmas compel researchers to critically think and examine values and make decisions that would balance gains, justice, and risk. When a researcher faces this situation of conflicting values, lack of clear solution, or pending consequences of decision, the researcher must balance the benefits, losses, and risks to make informed decisions devoid of unethical biases.
2. **Conflicting Interest:** When researchers' personal interest clash with the interests of the subjects or other stakeholders, there may exist some complications. When a researcher is under pressure to deliver and decides to put his/her interest ahead of participants' interest, there may be disagreements. However, the ethics of research must be considered a priority in all research activities.
3. **Lack of Clear Ethical Guidelines:** Some fields have no established proper ethical guidelines or limits that can guide researchers, thereby presenting a series of hurdles for researchers carrying out their jobs. Efforts must be made to put in place adequate ethical guidelines in all fields that will shape researchers' decisions and behaviors.
4. **Inadequate Training:** When there is lack or inadequate training of researchers, especially the younger ones, there will be difficulties in research ethics. Training and re-training offer researchers the opportunities to understand ethical principles and their applications in different research fields, research design, methods, and practicalities in conducting research. Additionally, meetings, conferences to share experience, network, and brainstorm with regulatory authorities and experts in various fields of research is crucial to having ethical research studies (The World Medical Association, n.d).
5. **Confidentiality:** Researchers are expected to treat information provided by subjects or stakeholders with confidential and they are also expected to be transparent and accountable to the research participants. Information gotten in the course of research study is treated with respect, including data from anonymous respondents. Most often than not many researchers do not adhere strictly with the guidelines on the protection of classified information in line with relevant standards. As a standard practice, researchers must keep the content of discussion with participants confidential to allow free and open discussions.

Methods for Addressing Ethical Challenges

Addressing ethical challenges in research is a critical aspect of scientific inquiry, ensuring that investigations are conducted with integrity, respect, and responsibility. Researchers often encounter complex ethical dilemmas that require careful consideration and thoughtful decision-making. Effective methods of addressing the challenges are essential for promoting trust, credibility, and validity in research findings. By employing a range of strategies and approaches, researchers can navigate ethical

complexities and ensure that their work is conducted in a manner that is respectful, responsible, and beneficiary to society. Some of the strategies include but are not limited to the following (Kapil Dev, 2024):

1. **Confidentiality and Anonymity:** Adherence to the principles of confidentiality and anonymity is crucial in research when there is need to protect the privacy of research participants. The data of the participants should be private and kept away from the public if such commitment is requested. Under no circumstance should a researcher release people's information without the people's approval.
2. **Informed Consent:** Informed consent is one of the foundations of research ethics because it defines the processes of getting people's readiness to participate in research. Participants are informed of the aims, objectives, legal implications and potential risks inherent in the study. Researchers must ensure that every participant understands the conditions for partaking and gives his/her full consent prior to commencement of the research.
3. **Balancing Risks and Benefits:** Conducting risk-benefit analysis prior to conducting study is advisable to enable researcher progress or stop the proposed study. It will also assist volunteers to make informed decisions about participating or not depending on the outcome of the risk-benefit analysis. Researchers must be sincere with volunteers on the results of the risk-benefit analysis. If warranted, researchers should perform a risk-benefit analysis. Research will progress if benefits outweigh potential harm and vice versa.
4. **Ethics Committees:** The fundamental role of the ethics committee in research is to advise researchers on the best practice of carrying out their research, considering the research ethics which are usually evaluated by this committee. The members of this committee are drawn from cross-functional teams including social sciences, Law, medicine, etc. The relevant ethics review board requests prior to commencement of the research, the study plan from the researcher for approval. Approval will either be granted or denied depending on the outcome of the evaluation.

Summary of the Findings of the Study

1. The study found out that, professional ethics in research are those standards and principles that guide researchers to conduct their work with the utmost accountability and total respect for subjects and stakeholders including the environment. The principles identified include: Respect for Person, Beneficence, Non-Maleficence, Autonomy, Justice, Honesty and Transparency, and Confidentiality and Privacy. While the importance of research ethics include: Protecting Human Subjects, Promoting Research Integrity, Maintaining Public Trust, Ensuring Validity and Reliability, and Fostering Responsible Innovation.
2. The study also found out that, ethical guidelines and codes provide the frameworks researchers and other stakeholders use in guarantying that research is carried out with utmost respect, integrity, and transparency to protect participants, demand accountability from researchers, and promote integrity of science. For instance, the Belmont Report of 1979 summarized the basic ethical principles identified by the Commission as three basic principles, among those generally accepted as cultural tradition are particularly relevant to the ethics of research involving human subjects: the principles of respect of persons, beneficence and justice.
3. The study equally found out ethical breaches, which include authorship disputes, conflict of interest, data manipulation, plagiarism, falsification, fabrication, etc., fabrication, falsification and plagiarism are regarded as the most grievous according to the Office of Science and Technology Policy (OSTP) in the executive office of the President of US (Elizabeth George, 2023). Also, as little as inappropriate authorship like assigning authors incorrectly is regarded as research misconduct.
4. Conversely, the study found out that, professional ethical codes have helped researchers avoid unethical behaviours. These codes are essential for protecting human subjects, promoting research integrity, and fostering a culture of responsibility. Some of these ethical codes cover the following areas: honesty and integrity, respect for intellectual property, transparency, responsible

and legal publication, confidentiality, carefulness, objectivity, animal care, and human subjects' protection (Md. Yeasir Arafat, 2024).

5. The study observed that, researchers face enormous challenges on ethics while carrying out their work due to lack of globally accepted standard method of research work, competing interest, absence of defined guidelines, etc. (Kapil Dev, 2024). Some of the challenges of research ethics include: Ethical dilemmas, conflicting interest, lack of clear ethical guidelines, inadequate training, and confidential.
6. Conclusively, the identifies the methods of addressing the ethical challenges confronting research. They include but not limited to: confidentiality and anonymity, informed consent, balancing risks and benefits, and establishment of an ethical committee. Effectively addressing these challenges is essential for promoting trust, credibility, and validity in research findings.

DISCUSSIONS

The importance of professional ethics in research cannot be overemphasized. Research ethics promote integrity, honesty, transparency, and respect for others and encourage researchers to treat subjects including environment with care which are needed for credible and socially beneficial results. In view of the findings from this paper, it is axiomatic that researchers are very much aware of the ethical principles yet there are series of ethical challenges facing research.

These challenges have adverse effect on researchers which often lead to grave competition, pressure to publish, request for sponsorship. When the challenges beget pressure, pressure on the other hand cause ethical compromises including fabrication, falsification and plagiarism, etc. These misconducts weaken the integrity of research which may cause adverse consequences for the researcher, institutions, or the society.

Within Nigerian context, the rising effects of pressure on academics and the push to “publish or perish” syndrome, have caused increase in unethical practices, like the many types of research misconduct which often diminish not only the quality and reliability of research, but jeopardize public trust in Nigerian academic institutions and research bodies.

Nigeria has made great efforts at aligning with professional ethical codes; however, there are still obvious gaps in implementation and oversight. Inadequate funding, inadequate knowledge, and poor enforcement authority have restrained ethics committees and review boards in most universities from discharging their duties. At times, research is carried out in these institutions without adequate ethical clearance due to low oversight functions.

Furthermore, absence of ethics education and awareness among young researchers lead to research misconduct. It is gladdening that the institutions in Nigeria have included ethics courses in their curriculum, at times; students leave the university environment without knowing their ethical responsibilities. This gap also causes inadvertent ethical breaches and encourages misconduct. Inconsistent disciplinary measures further add to growing cases of misconduct. Another issue is the academic dishonesty which are often treated internally and informally leading to no consequences. If this wrong narrative persists, unethical practice will continue to thrive.

To strengthen the ethical framework, institutions must ensure ethics training is not optional, review boards should be funded and empowered to monitor compliance to promote culture of integrity. In Nigeria, the national research bodies like National Health Research Ethics Committee (NHREC) and the Tertiary Education Trust Fund (TETFUND) must work together to ensure promotion of ethical standards. Research in Nigeria must uphold highest ethical standard to ensure not only the credibility of research outcome, but also to boost the country's academic reputation.

CONCLUSION

To have a credible, reliable, and generally acceptable research outcome, the cardinal ethical principles such as integrity, honesty, human dignity, objectivity, accountability, informed consent, respect for intellectual property, etc must be upheld with tenacity. There are always severe consequences including

legal disputes, erosion of public trust, reputational damage, low respect for academia and host of other derision when there are ethical lapses in research; especially when the research is supposed to influence national policy, societal well-being and economic development.

This paper has identified total adherence to professional ethics as sacrosanct if research must be acceptable to all. Research misconduct such as plagiarism, fabrication, falsification and more create a lot of mistrust thereby undermining the integrity of research. Promotion of robust ethical culture within our research institutions, research regulators, and other stakeholders is not optional, but indispensable for economic growth, academic excellence and a sane society.

In some climes like Nigeria, lack of capacity-building initiatives, poor regulatory presence, inadequate mentoring, and inordinate pressure to publish, contribute to violation of ethical principles, although no reason is good to justify this misconduct.

RECOMMENDATIONS

In view of the findings recorded in this paper, the following recommendations have been put forward to change the negative narratives.

1. **Promoting Culture of integrity:** Promoting culture of integrity entails use of carrot and stick in the modelling of ethical behavior by the relevant stakeholders. The reward system should be extended to those who have demonstrated strong adherence to ethical principles while releasing the sledgehammer on the heads of those who intentionally violate the revered guidelines. Fostering.
2. **Development and Enforcement of National Ethical Guidelines:** The research stakeholders which include professional bodies, research institutions, universities, relevant private bodies should help to keep sanity in the research field through the creation of robust codes of ethics that clearly states both acceptable and unacceptable behaviors in research. These formulated guidelines must be made compulsory to all players in research and followed by oversight functions by relevant committees. The guidelines, like every other document, should be reviewed periodically to reflect current challenges.
3. **Compulsory Ethics Training and Mentorship:** Relevant bodies in research should not only integrate ethics into research training but ensure ethics education is a prerequisite. Periodic workshops, and seminars will boost the adherence to ethical standards. These interventions will address both present challenges and dilemmas of research ethics faced by both old and younger researchers.
4. **Empowering Institutional Review Boards:** The bodies that carry out oversight functions, like Research Ethics Committee, Ethics Review Board, etc must be strengthened and funded to be independent. These bodies must operate in a transparent manner and ensure they have documented work procedures to garner public trust. Their function must be well defined which may include reviewing research proposals, oversight functions, evaluation of research results, among others. They should have authority to stop identified unethical behavior and make recommendations to relevant authority for disciplinary action.
5. **Protection of Whistleblowers:** To monitor compliance to established guidelines, the relevant institutions must have means of reporting ethical violations through anonymous channels. These anonymous reporters must be protected from discrimination, or hatred. For fair hearing, every reported case must be thoroughly investigated.
6. **Use of Robust Technology:** Use of reliable technology can be deployed for the detection of research misconduct like plagiarism, inappropriate authorship, data manipulation, etc. This method has in the past helped in detecting various misconducts, these tools should be upgraded to do more. To promote compliance and strengthen positive research outcomes, relevant research bodies should invest in technology.

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